

Audio file

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Transcript

Speaker 1

So hello. Thank you so much for taking the time to be part of this interview. My name is Anna Makarudze, and I'm pursuing a master's in software engineering at the Taking Institute of Technology. And my research seeks to investigate how developers and maintainers perceive vulnerabilities in open source dependencies, and especially with the rise of supply chain attacks. So my study focuses on developers, contributors, and from five web frameworks, Django, Next.js, Springboot, Laravel, and Ruby on Rails.

And participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw from the interview at any time. It will not retain any personal data or identifiable information. The name, role, e-mail address, and any identifiable details will not be published or shared with anyone. You can skip any questions you're not comfortable answering, and your responses will remain anonymous. And then the index will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow the supervisors to verify the identity of the reported data, after which they'll be deleted.

And we conform to the GDPR guideline.

Before we start, maybe you can introduce yourself. You can mention the projects that you are involved with, your role in those projects. Are you a developer or maintainer or contributor? And I think your experience level with software development, how many years you've been in the industry and how many years you've been working with that web framework. So you can also mention the web framework that you are aligned to and any other projects within that web framework that you are aligned to.

Speaker 2

Yes, so my name is

I have currently 19 years of experience in web development, and also at least 11 or 12 in the open source world, being a contributor at the beginning, and then also a maintainer of open source packages. I'm still a maintainer of Django requests package.

I'm still a member of various teams in the Django organization. I'm a Django merger, I'm a member of the Django triage and review team. I'm a member of the Django operations team, security team, releases, releasers team, and so on. I was also a Django fellow, so one of the paid contractors that maintained Django for five years from 2014 to 2019. I would need to check the correct dates. It was five years.

So I'm also a contributor of dozens of open source packages, mainly from the Django ecosystem, but I'm also a contributor of CPython and a few others outside of Django and Python world. That's my short introduction.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And can you sort of describe what you do in Django? You mentioned being a member of many teams. Can you describe what you do in those teams?

Speaker 2

Yeah. So as a member of operations team, operations team, I'm responsible for infrastructure that we are using in Django organization, both for our website and for our CI. So we have a separate Jenkins installation with a few nodes that are responsible for running tests and so on. So as a part of OPS team, I'm responsible for keeping it alive. And as a member of the security, I'm responsible for handling security reports that we receive at security@djangoproject.com to help judge if it's a valid security issue or not, how we should reply and so on. As a releaser, I'm responsible for releasing any versions of Django. So this is mainly handled by the current paid contractors, current Django Fellows, but from time to time, I also release a new version of Django. As a Django merger, I'm responsible for reviewing patches, and also I have rights to actually merge changes into the Django itself. And it partly overlaps with being a member of the triage and review team which are responsible for reviewing patches and also for guiding new contributors, how to create a patch that can be merged into Django itself. So what kind of guidelines they should follow, what kind of rules do we have inside our organization, and so on, just to make patch valid and mergeable, I would say.

Speaker 1

So you've mentioned many projects that you're part of, including Django. And do any of these projects use packages from other ecosystems, for example, maybe from JavaScript ecosystem?

Speaker 2

Yeah. So in Django, we are quite I would say assertive about dependencies. So the main Python part of Django has currently only two, I think, two, maybe three dependencies and some optional ones that you may or may not use if you want, but basically Django is able to work on its own without an extensive ecosystem of third-party packages.

The only one that we are currently using, or most of the ones that we are currently using, are also handled by us. So one of the hard dependencies of Django is asgiref package, but it is also maintained by the Django organization, for example, yeah. So we are totally aware of what's inside this package and how we build it and what's, you know, inside. We are responsible for the content and code that is there. And the only place when we actually use a third JavaScript libraries is in the Django admin where we have few, I would say, external dependencies, but most of them are optional, like JavaScript libraries for handling geo data, for example, libraries like OpenLayer and so on. You can use them, but you don't need to, and so on. They are not hard dependencies. They are dependencies that you can add if you want to use some features in the admin and and so on. Yeah.

Speaker 2

So we have few. But in most of cases they are optional.

Speaker 1

And you mentioned that you are part of the security team. And how are security issue report reports managed in the project?

Speaker 2

So we are trying to change it now. So previously it was just a mailing list that all members of the Django security team receive emails reported by by researchers or by contributors. And then in the few days or weeks, we replied with our decision what we what we what we want to do with this security report. Is it valid or not? do we are we going to actually implement patch and research security really is related with that or not. So most of the discussion was inside this mailing list or because we also have a bounty program. We also use hacker one for for security reports. So it is an external portal when when folks can send security reports. And then if it's valid and we actually have to patch it, then they will receive some bounty for valid reports.

Speaker 1

And how aware are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependents present to your projects? You know, outside of the Django projects, maybe the other projects that you will want.

Speaker 2

I'm trying to be closer to the back end than to the front end. And I think that it's-- I'm aware that it's an issue. But I also hope that it's less an issue in Python's world than it is in JavaScript world, mainly because there are many batteries included with Django and also with Python which is not the case for JavaScript.

So JavaScript is barely a bare language without any batteries included. And then there are plenty of small dependencies that people are using without actually knowing what's inside and how it's implemented. That's why I would say in JavaScript world, it's more often and easier to actually inject dependency mainly because, you know, all small functionalities had to be implemented by someone. And then, you know, it's easier to spread that kind of libraries across ecosystem than it is in the Python's world, because in Python and Django, we are using first-party packages mainly to add, I would say, more complicated features.

So the code that is behind them need to work well and so on. So you need to actually build a valuable functionality and then try to inject something in there. Another thing is that when you have actually a valuable functionality, then people would need to start to use it. And when they start to use it, they also start to, you know, send requests for changes.

They are also starting to send patches and more people are aware what's inside the code and how it works. If you have a tiny JavaScript libraries that are doing a single thing, No one really cares what's inside. You know, if they want to use it like, you know, a small hook to, I don't know, to perform some simple regular expression or to, you know, do things like that. Yeah. A small tiny bits that just work. Yeah.

In Python and Django to actually Add any dependencies, you need to have available functionality that people would like to use. And if you have, then someone will definitely try to contribute to this package and, you know, be aware how it works and what's inside the code.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And how aware are you of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects?

Speaker 2

I'm aware that that kind of things exist. And so currently we are using, we are using maybe outside of Django, but we are using some external tools just to check the entire dependency tree and see what's inside and what we will use here for that.

For that, we are using built-in things like scanners built-in to GitHub or GitLab or another tool that you are using to keep your repository that actually help to resolve the entire

dependency tree and see what's inside, report to you constantly about security issues that were found there, and also give you pretty quick information if something is something in your dependency tree has been corrupted, for example.

Speaker 1

Okay, can you? Are you able to name some of the tools that you're using for for that?

00:14:30 Speaker 2

Yeah, for so in in my page app we are using Nessus. It is a tool that give us both security reports about packages, but also about libraries used directly in Docker images and things like that. So it reports us constantly about security, security issues, about the severity and, you know, how to manage them. So this is one tool. We also use built-in GitLab vulnerability reports. And yeah, so tools like that.

Speaker 1

And do these tools help you to identify vulnerabilities within the dependencies in your project?

00:15:43 Speaker 2

Fortunately, fortunately not, at least for now. Okay.

Speaker 1

So how do you identify dependents that are actually vulnerable within your project?

Speaker 2

So, you know, we try to be really careful about about all about about all dependencies that we are using. And we also have, you know, we also use pinned versions of dependencies. Then if we actually decided to upgrade from version to version, then we are checking changes that were made in third party packages, just to be sure that it's it's still properly maintained by the same people, for example, that reads the previous version, that there is no change in the way how it's managed and who is responsible for this library that we used and so on.

It gives us, I think, that's pretty good confidence that the next version that we would like to upgrade to is still, you know, in good hands. So there's a level of trust, I would say, between us and maintainers, but it is also a level of trust built for many years.

Yeah, it's yeah, it's how it was for many years. And I think it's still works pretty well. I'm also maybe, you know, it's maybe also easier for me because as a person really heavily involved

in the open source work, I can say that I even, you know, personally knows a lot of maintainers of packages that we are using.

So, you know, I know this works and I'm also I'm always pretty careful about adding new dependency, especially if I don't know its maintainer. And then I need to check carefully who's responsible for this package and how it looks like, just to be sure that there's nothing to be worried about.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And what influences the decision to update to newer versions of dependencies within your project? Do you simply upgrade? Because there's a newer version. You mentioned that you pin dependencies between versions. So when do you actually decide? And what what makes you decide to upgrade to the new efficient?

Speaker 2

First of all, we decided to upgrade if there is any requirement changes. So if Any of the libraries change the requirements. So, you know, to update one library, we need to update another one. Yeah, that's one of scenario.

The second is, if we want to use the main tool that we are using, like, for example, if we want to upgrade the Django framework, then we need to go to our dependencies and check for our new versions that will support the new version of Django, for example. That's, I would say, the second cinder.

Or the third one is if there is any security release in third-party packages, then we upgrade it. But it's not a constant process. It's not that we are upgrading every time when the new release will appear yet. We are doing this only if we need to or if we want to because there is some new feature that we want to use that is in any version.

So we don't have any constant upgrades here. It's not that we have dependabot in start and we are doing, you know, and we are blindly applying all new versions just because they are new versions.

Speaker 1

And how do you, mentioned that you, when you're updating, you check whether the maintenance, maintenance of the project are still the same. How do you check maintenance of dependencies of your project? Because sometimes maintenance or maybe developed by creators of projects tend to abandon their project.

So how, yes, how do you know, how do you? know when dependencies have been abandoned and no longer being maintained.

Speaker 2

Yeah. Speaker 2

So we're not only so. So first of all, maintenance are mentioned in PyPi directly. Secondly, when we decide to upgrade a new, when we decide to upgrade a package, then we are always changing, checking its change log, and so on. So we need to In most cases, you need to go directly to the repository to see what kind of changes were made. And for that, you need to go to GitLab or GitHub to check a project and its code. And then you can check who released a new version, for example. Then we can see that this is a different person that released a previous one, for example the the previous one that we had current that we currently have been so we can see how how it was changed and and who's was responsible for this new version.

Speaker 1

And how do you handle vulnerable dependencies within your project? You mentioned that it's not like you use dependable to check everything. So how do you know when you have vulnerable dependencies and how do you handle them.

Speaker 2

Yeah, so we are using building reports from GitLab and also from Nessus related with new security releases. Yeah, so if there's a new security release, then we have this weekly task to check the new security report that mentioned to us a specific version of library, which is vulnerable. It describes vulnerability, and in which version it was solved. And then we are deciding if we should apply it instantly, or it can wait, and so on.

Speaker 1

And how long does it take to update the vulnerable dependence within your project normally?

Speaker 2

Less than a week.

Speaker 1

Less than a week. Okay.

Speaker 2

That's for sure. Okay.

Speaker 1

And how do you handle one of the dependencies that are no longer being maintained? Suppose the dependence is no longer being maintained, but it has appeared in your report.

Speaker 2

Then we search for a substitution. So we are changing for a tool that we do. similar thing. Or if not, then as a large set of sort, we can always incorporate its logic into our project itself and make us responsible for maintaining it from that moment.

Speaker 1

So, One thing in the Django communities, if the package is used by many people and the maintainer steps away, people tend to take it over maybe through organisations like Jazz Band and Django Commons. How difficult is this to do when the dependency is outside of the ecosystem? For example, maybe a JavaScript library that you're using in Django, it's no longer being maintained.

Speaker 2

So if we have a nested layer of dependencies, yeah, and some of them are vulnerable, then we need to decide what to do with the one that is using this library. One, because I'm an open source person, so my first reaction will be to reach, to maintain this package that are using and of the vulnerable one and, you know, try to help them to upgrade it or to do not use it. And if not, then we need to decide if there's a different package that are not using this nested dependency and so on. So I would say that the first thing would be to reach to the main term of package that we are using directly and try to help them to get rid of this vulnerable dependency. And if that won't help, then we need to decide to use a different one or, you know, to move this functionality into our project directly.

Speaker 1

Okay. And, okay. And if any of the projects that you've worked on ever been exposed to supply chain attack?

Speaker 2

For now, I think not. I think no, no.

Speaker 1

Okay. And what factors help you to address vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

Speaker 2

Sorry, can you repeat?

Speaker 1

I'm saying, okay, what helps you to address vulnerable dependencies in your projects? Are they tools or?

Speaker 2

What helps me update my dependencies? Yeah. So currently, we are using. Currently, we are using. We are using pip tools to to to have actually pinned the entire dependency tree. Yeah. So at the first level, we have a list of packages that we are using directly, and it basically resolves it to the, with the list of all nested dependencies and also make us aware which packet is required by which one. And then also to be able to pin specific versions also for nested packages. So for that, we are using pip tools and pip compile command just to like resolve or compile our short direct dependency list to extended dependency list with all necessary requirements. We used that. In the past, I also used Poetry for that.

Speaker 1

OK. And are there any challenges you face when trying to address vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Maybe not to address. There are some challenges to make a proper judgment, to know that you are actually vulnerable to the things, to issues that appear in this package. This can be quite challenging to actually judge. Do you need to you know, upgrade instantly or wait, are we affected by the security issue at all? Because maybe not. And you know, there is nothing to to be worried about. And you know, we can upgrade with the new release without providing any hotfix and do this instantly. And so on. So this is quite a tricky thing to actually judge if you are affected or not. And and how by by security issues. No, it would be probably easier to judge if security issues and or CVEs and so on will be described better than they are in many cases. Like, you know, it's quite often that there is only a slogan and that's it. Yeah, it's, you know, cross site something in this package.

And it's hard to judge where it is in what kind of tools, what kind of functions are affected and so on, you know. Then you need to go to this package to check security pattern actually just on your own if you are affected or not.

So this is definitely a tricky part.

Speaker 1

All right. And what recommendations do you have for dependence management for mitigate supply chain attack?

Speaker 2

Can you repeat?

Speaker 1

I'm saying, what recommendations do you have for open source dependence management so that people don't find themselves exposed to supply chain attacks?

Speaker 2

If they are already exposed to that, yeah.

Speaker 1

Yes, if they are not exposed to them, how can you make sure that you manage your dependencies in such a way that you don't find yourself being exposed to attacks through your dependencies.

Speaker 2

Yeah, so I think that the basic thing is to be aware what you have in your stack. So all kind of tools that resolve your dependency tree and give you a total list of things that you are actually injecting into your project.

It is the basic thing that we all should do. That's the first thing that really helps to increase awareness of what we are using. So I would say that that's the first thing. And the second is to be less I would say eager to add dependencies for everything that you can, instead of writing a code on your own. Because sometimes dependencies that we are using are really tiny, like, you know, 10 lines of code or a single class and so on. It can be easily handled by your own. And yes, sometimes it's better to keep it in your own code than to use third party package.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much for taking your time to experience this interview. I think that's all for me. Well, thank you and enjoy the rest of your day.

Speaker 2

Thanks. I hope that I was helpful.

Speaker 1

Yes, very helpful. Thank you.